

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**MATERNAL COMPLICATIONS IN TWIN PREGNANCY;
RECENT TRENDS: A STUDY AT JINNAH HOSPITAL
LAHORE**¹Hassnat Ahmed Alvi, ²Dr. Sidra, ³Noor Dawood¹Basic Health Unit Thatta Kheru Matmal, Hafizabad, hassnatalvi@gmail.com²Hayat Memorial Hospital, Lahore, drsidra1994@gmail.com³Rural Health Dispensary Dograi Khurd, Lahore, sweetcancerian_16@gmail.com**Article Received:** October 2019 **Accepted:** November 2019 **Published:** December 2019**Abstract:****Objective-** The objective of this study is to analyze the complication during twin pregnancy**Methodology-** This study was done on the women who had the pregnancy age around twenty weeks at Jinnah hospital. All the data was collected from the delivery room of Jinnah hospital. Patients who had problem like hypertension and diabetes were exclude from research**Results-** In collected data 19539 was the total delivery cases in which 432 were the cases of twin pregnancy or one can say that in every 1000 cases 22 was the twin pregnancy cases. 282 out of 432 was the referred patients and 87% of the patients were lying in the age group of 21 to 30 years. Out of 432 304 gave birth to premature twines 45.7% were contributed to primigravida. 259 patients out of 432 had anemia, in 122 hypertension was found, in 120 membranes preterm rupture, in 20 problem of diabetes, in 44 postpartum haemorrhage and in 24 cholesterol complication were noticed and in two cases maternal mortality occurred.**Conclusion-** From this study in various cases the percentage of various kind of complication were found in case of twin pregnancy. This study showed that in case of twin pregnancy a higher number of patients were observed of having the disorders like anemia, hypertension and preterm labor. More step should be taken to provide all the medication to avoid maternal mortality due to premature delivery cases. Proper treatment should be provided to lessen the adversity of complications during pregnancy.**Keywords:** Twin pregnancy, Preeclampsia, Preterm rupture of membranes, Preterm labor, Multiple pregnancies**Corresponding author:****Hassnat Ahmed Alvi,**

Basic Health Unit Thatta Kheru Matmal, Hafizabad, hassnatalvi@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press *Hassnat Ahmed Alvi et al., Maternal Complications In Twin Pregnancy; Recent Trends: A Study At Jinnah Hospital Lahore., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(12).*

INTRODUCTION:

In spite of the fact that, frequency of multiple pregnancies is changes as indicated by equality of patients, age and race, due to the treatments of enhancing the fertility increasing rate of multiple pregnancy rate is increasing. From the period of antenatal to postpartum, the maternal complication are increasing Premature delivery is the most common and severe type of complication which is one of the main reason of maternal mortality. Monochorionic pregnancies like conflicting twin, twin turned around blood vessel perfusion arrangement, twin - twin transfusion disorder, intrinsic oddities and single fetal death are the most fatal complications in case of twin cases. These chronic complications should be treated in a proper way to avoid mortality. Increased heart beat and adverse anemia are the most common complication causing the mortality. In various cases of pregnancies hypertension and diabetes was also observed and these all collectively could be a reason of maternal mortality. Postpartum hemorrhage is also observed in various

cases of pregnancies 2% of maternal mortality is due to this. To minimize the too much loss of blood for preventing the clot breakdown in surgery anti-fibrinolytic agents are commonly used. More step should be taken to provide all the medication to avoid maternal mortality due to premature delivery cases. Proper treatment should be provided to lessen the adversity of complications during pregnancy. World health organization is focusing on the establishment of health care center so that these complication can be diagnosed in its early stages and proper treatment can be provided. This study was planned to diagnosed various kind of complication in case of twin pregnancy in Jinnah hospital Lahore.

METHODOLOGY:

This study was done on the women who had the pregnancy age around twenty weeks at Jinnah hospital. All the data was collected from the delivery room of Jinnah hospital. Patients who had problem like hypertension and diabetes were exclude from research

Table 1: Complications in case of twin pregnancy.

Maternal complications	Percentage
Antenatal complications	
Total Preterm delivery	304 (70%)
Spontaneous preterm delivery	272 (89.4)
Induced preterm delivery	32 (10.5%)
PTROM	120 (39.4%)
Route of delivery	
Vaginal delivery	212 (49.1%)
LSCS	224 (51.9%)
Anaemia	259 (60%)
Mild	103 (39.7%)
Moderate	139 (53.6%)
Severe	17 (6.5%)
Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy	122(28.3%)
Cholestasis of pregnancy	24 (5.5%)
Hypothyroidism	22 (5.1%)
Antepartum hemorrhage (APH)	20 (4.6%)
Toxaemic abruptio	09 (2.06%)
Nontoxemic abruptio	07 (1.5%)
Placenta previa	04 (0.93%)
Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM)	08 (1.8%)
Postpartum complications	
Atonic postpartum haemorrhage	44 (10.2%)
Maternal mortality	02 (0.46%)

The above data was collected from the delivery room of Jinnah hospital Lahore, in each case pregnancy age at the time of birth, maternal age, route of delivery and parity was recoded. Above are some complications that were collected from the data for example in case of postpartum complications the number of maternal mortality, and PPH, severity of anemia in patients, hypertension cases placenta previa, GDM etc. PPH was defined when 500ml blood loss during vaginal delivery and 1litre during cesarean section or more than this lead to the PPH.

Statistical Investigation:

In SPSS v22 data was analyzed and in terms of percentages and frequency data was expressed

RESULTS:

During this research 432 was taken in an these 432 only one patients was found to have diabetes mellitus, so from this study no association of diabetes mellitus can be proved with the pregnancy cases. In collected data 19539 was the total delivery cases in which 432 were the cases of twin pregnancy or one can say that in every 1000 cases 22 was the twin pregnancy cases. 282 out of 432 was the referred patients and 87% of the patients were lying in the age group of 21 to 30 years. Antenatal complication was categorizes into induced preterm delivery and spontaneous preterm delivery and out of 432, 304 i.e. 70% gave birth to premature twines that is total preterm delivery in which 272 were the delivery case of spontaneous preterm and rest of the 32 were induced preterm delivery cases. The route of delivery of 212 patients was vaginal while the delivery route of 224 was LSCS. 45.7% were contributed to primigravida. 259 patients out of 432 had anemia, in 122 hypertension was found, in 120 membranes preterm rupture, in 20 problem of diabetes, in 44 postpartum haemorrhage and in 24 cholesterol complication were noticed and in two cases maternal mortality occurred.

DISCUSSION:

In this study it was found that in every 1000 patients 22 delivery cases were twin cases. In spite of the fact that, frequency of multiple pregnancies is changes as indicated by equality of patients, age and race, due to the treatments of enhancing the fertility increasing rate of multiple pregnancy rate is increasing. In this study it was found that the maternal age of 86.7% of women was between 21 to 30 years in most the twin cases. According to a study multiple pregnancy occurs during the age of 21 to 29 years. This high occurrence of multiple pregnancy is youth marriage and childbirth in the early age of maternal. From the period of

antenatal to postpartum, the maternal complication are increasing Premature delivery is the most common and severe type of complication which is one of the main reason of maternal mortality.. Increased heart beat and adverse anemia are the most common complication causing the mortality. In various cases of pregnancies hypertension and diabetes was also observed and these all collectively could be a reason of maternal mortality. Monochorionic pregnancies like conflicting twin, twin turned around blood vessel perfusion arrangement, twin - twin transfusion disorder, intrinsic oddities and single fetal death are the most fatal complications in case of twin cases. These chronic complications should be treated in a proper way to avoid mortality. During this research 432 was taken in an these 432 only one patients was found to have diabetes mellitus, so from this study no association of diabetes mellitus can be proved with the pregnancy cases.

Primigravida were 45.7% and multigravida added to 54.3% of twin incubations. According to a study¹⁵ increasingly number of preterm conveyances in multigravida when contrasted with primigravida patients. In a study¹⁴ revealed preterm cases of delivery in 60% and 67% of twin pregnancies respectively. The acquired danger of preterm delivery in various pregnancies is bolstered by higher rate of preterm delivery in this investigation, out of 304 (70%) preterm cases 304 i.e. 70% gave birth to premature twines that is total preterm delivery in which 272 were the delivery case of spontaneous preterm and rest of the 32 were induced preterm delivery cases. The route of delivery of 212 patients was vaginal while the delivery route of 224 was LSCS. More step should be taken to provide all the medication to avoid maternal mortality due to premature delivery cases. Proper treatment should be provided to lessen the adversity of complications during pregnancy. During this research 432 was taken in an these 432 only one patients was found to have diabetes mellitus, so from this study no association of diabetes mellitus can be proved with the pregnancy cases.

CONCLUSION:

This study revealed the greater number of multiple pregnancy cases having the complications like hypertension anemia as compared to other studies. From this study in various cases the percentage of various kind of complication were found in case of twin pregnancy. This study showed that in case of twin pregnancy a higher number of patients were observed of having the disorders like anemia, hypertension and

preterm labor. More step should be taken to provide all the medication to avoid maternal mortality due to premature delivery cases. Proper treatment should be provided to lessen the adversity of complications during pregnancy.

REFERENCE:

- Practice committee of american society for reproductive medicine. Multiple gestation associated with infertility therapy: an American Society for Reproductive Medicine Practice Committee opinion. *Fertil Steril* 2012; 97:825.
- Lisonkova S, Joseph KS, Bell R, Glinianaia SV. Effect of advanced maternal age on perinatal outcomes in twins: the impact of chorionicity. *Ann Epidemiol.* 2013 Jul 1;23(7):428-34.
- Nkyekyer K. Multiple pregnancy. In: Kwawukume EY, Emuveyan EE, editors. *Comprehensive Obstetrics in the Tropics*. 1st ed. Asante and Hittscher Printing Press Limited; 2002. p. 162-72.
- Adashi EY. Seeing double: a nation of twins from sea to shining sea. *Obstetr Anesthesia Digest.* 2017 Mar 1;37(1):16.
- Hamilton BE, Martin JA, Osterman MJ, Curtin SC, Matthews TJ. Births: Final data for 2014. *Natl Vital Stat Rep.* 2015;64(2):1-64.
- Hack KE, Derks JB, Elias SG, Franx A, Roos EJ, Voerman SK, et al. Increased perinatal mortality and morbidity in monochorionic versus dichorionic twin pregnancies: clinical implications of a large Dutch cohort study. *BJOG: Int J Obstetr Gynaecol.* 2008 Jan 1;115(1):58-67.
- Kametas NA, McAuliffe F, Kramp E, Chambers J, Nicolaidis KH. Maternal cardiac function in twin pregnancy. *Obstetr Gynecol.* 2003 Oct 1;102(4):806-15.
- Sibai BM, Hauth J, Caritis S, Lindheimer MD, MacPherson C, Klebanoff M, et al. Hypertensive disorders in twin versus singleton gestations. *Am J Obstetr Gynecol.* 2000 Apr 1;182(4):938-42.
- Rao A, Sairam S, Shehata H. Obstetric complications of twin pregnancies. *Best Prac Res Clin Obstet Gynaecol.* 2004 Aug 1;18(4):557-76.
- Buhling KJ, Henrich W, Starr E, Lubke M, Bertram S, Siebert G, Dudenhausen JW. Risk for gestational diabetes and hypertension for women with twin pregnancy compared to singleton pregnancy. *Arch of Gynecol Obstetr.* 2003 Nov 1;269(1):33-6.
- Ananth CV, Demissie K, Smulian JC, Vintzileos AM. Placenta previa in singleton and twin births in the United States, 1989 through 1998: a comparison of risk factor profiles and associated conditions. *Am J Obstetr Gynecol.* 2003 Jan 1;188(1):275-81.
- Santana DS, Cecatti JG, Surita FG, Silveira C, Costa ML, Souza JP, et al. Twin pregnancy and severe maternal outcomes: the World Health Organization multicountry survey on maternal and newborn health. *Obstetr Gynecol.* 2016 Apr 1;127(4):631-41.
- Implementation of the ANC guideline and recommendations. WHO recommendations on antenatal care for a positive pregnancy experience. 2016;4:105-7.
- Deepthi HR, Pradeep MR, Lalitha S. Retrospective study of maternal and perinatal outcome of twin pregnancy in a teaching hospital. *J Dental Med Sci.* 2015;14(1): 29-32.
- Tomar SP, Kushwah SS, Kushwah AP. Association of sociodemographic factors with multiple births and birth outcomes in comparison to single births among deliveries conducted at a tertiary hospital in Rewa, Madhya Pradesh. *Int J Students' Res.* 2014 Jan 1;4(1):8.
- Rezavand N, Veisi F, Malek-Khosravi S, Zangeneh M, Kohzadi M. Assessment of Frequency of Twin Pregnancy and Neonatal Outcome in Deliveries of Mo'tazedi Hospital, Kermanshah in 2004-2007. *J Obstetr Gynecol India.* 2014 Feb 1;64(1):19-22.
- Nandmer GK, Kanhere AV. Study of obstetric and fetal outcome of twin pregnancy in a tertiary care centre. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstetr Gynecol.* 2017 Feb 19;4(6):1789-92.
- Shetty MB, Shivananjaiah C, Swarup A. A retrospective study: twin gestation at tertiary care, maternal and fetal outcome. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstetr Gynecol.* 2016 Dec 16;5(1):217-9.
- Chowdhury S, Hussain MA. Maternal complications in twin pregnancies. *Mymensingh Med J.* 2011 Jan;20(1):83-7.
- Sheela SR, Patila A. A study of maternal and fetal outcome in multifetal gestation at a rural based teaching hospital-a retrospective analysis. *Int J Biol Med Res.* 2014;5(2):3994-7.
- Assunção RA, Liao AW, Brizot MD, Krebs VL, Zugaib M. Perinatal outcome of twin pregnancies delivered in a teaching hospital. *J Brazilian Med Ass.* 2010;56(4):447-51.
- Gonzalez MC, Reyes H, Arrese M, Figueroa D, Lorca B, Andresen M, et al. Intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy in twin pregnancies. *J Hepatol.* 1989 Jul;9(1):84-90.